

New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 108

The work is also available at the following link:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10016>

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Abstract

*For the first time in history of magic squares, this work brings different kinds of magic squares. These are double digits **cornered** magic squares. The work is for the orders 5 to 108. From order 82 onwards the magic squares are **semi-magic**. The also worked on cornered magic squares in different ways up to order 24 [83, 84, 85]. The examples given in this work are only up to order 30. Further orders are available as excel files. These are in two parts. One from order 5 to 81, and second from order 82 to 108. The second part is still as **semi-magic** squares.*

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Contents

1 Introduction	2
2 Cornered Magic Squares	3
3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	23

1 Introduction

Recently, author worked with **cornered magic squares** based on two-by-two digits:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6 [83].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13 [83].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24 [85].

Also, the author worked on **double digits bordered** magic squares. This works starts from order 8 and goes up to order 40:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24 [87].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22 [70].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30 [71].
4. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32 [88].
5. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Order 34 and 38 [73].
6. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40[72].

1. Inder J. Taneja, Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15 [74].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Orders 17 and 19 [75].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Orders 21 and 23 [76].
4. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Order 25 [77].
5. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Order 27 [78].
6. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Order 29 [79].
7. Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares of Order 31 [80].

Recently, author wrote a complete work on **double digits bordered** magic squares from order 7 to 108 [81, 82].

This work is an extension of **cornered** magics squares. It goes up to order 81. Above work on **cornered** magic squares is extended-type. In this work we have just given one example in each case. Since the number is high, an excel file is also attached with the work.

2 Cornered Magic Squares

5x5	mgc					65	6x6	mgc					111	7x7	mgc						175		
	16	11	12	23	3	65		17	22	11	24	29	8	111		26	21	28	30	20	8	42	175
	9	13	17	25	1	65		12	23	18	21	27	10	111		27	25	23	33	17	12	38	175
	14	15	10	7	19	65		26	13	20	15	35	2	111		22	29	24	14	36	48	2	175
	5	6	22	8	24	65		19	16	25	14	9	28	111		34	32	31	13	15	45	5	175
	21	20	4	2	18	65		4	3	36	30	6	32	111		16	18	19	35	37	10	40	175
©IJT	65	65	65	65	65	65		33	34	1	7	5	31	111		46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175
							©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111		4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175
														©IJT	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

8x8	pan		260	9x9	mgc		369			
	31	36	25	38	43	22	13	52	260	
	26	37	32	35	23	42	1	64	260	
	40	27	34	29	41	24	54	11	260	
	33	30	39	28	49	16	9	56	260	
	18	17	44	50	20	46	7	58	260	
	47	48	21	15	19	45	53	12	260	
	10	8	62	51	6	61	60	2	260	
	55	57	3	14	59	4	63	5	260	
©IJT	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	
	38	43	42	50	32	27	55	15	67	369
	45	41	37	46	36	62	20	8	74	369
	40	39	44	49	33	26	56	80	2	369
	34	35	52	31	53	65	17	10	72	369
	48	47	30	29	51	23	59	14	68	369
	60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369
	22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369
	78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369
	4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369
©IJT	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

10x10	mgc		505	11x11	mgc		671					
	49	54	43	56	61	40	31	70	18	83	505	
	44	55	50	53	41	60	19	82	5	96	505	
	58	45	52	47	59	42	72	29	94	7	505	
	51	48	57	46	67	34	27	74	99	2	505	
	36	35	62	68	38	64	25	76	95	6	505	
	65	66	39	33	37	63	71	30	10	91	505	
	28	26	80	69	24	79	78	20	88	13	505	
	73	75	21	32	77	22	81	23	8	93	505	
	15	84	12	90	9	98	97	85	1	14	505	
	86	17	89	11	92	3	4	16	87	100	505	
©IJT	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	
	58	63	62	54	68	43	79	87	35	13	109	671
	65	61	57	55	67	78	44	25	97	104	18	671
	60	59	64	72	50	75	47	24	98	8	114	671
	56	52	53	73	71	38	84	89	33	3	119	671
	66	70	69	51	49	39	83	92	30	106	16	671
	81	37	40	76	77	74	42	29	93	5	117	671
	41	85	82	46	45	80	48	23	99	105	17	671
	21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
	101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
©IJT	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

12x12	mgc													870
		66	67	77	80	86	59	54	91	23	122	134	11	870
		79	76	70	65	64	81	41	104	118	27	18	127	870
		74	69	75	72	58	87	97	48	106	39	9	136	870
		71	78	68	73	83	62	44	101	28	117	141	4	870
		55	82	61	60	88	89	98	47	121	24	126	19	870
		90	63	84	85	56	57	100	45	31	114	140	5	870
		103	92	99	43	49	93	51	50	38	107	123	22	870
		42	53	46	102	96	52	95	94	120	25	135	10	870
		26	40	30	36	112	34	110	116	108	113	21	124	870
		119	105	115	109	33	111	35	29	32	37	14	131	870
		1	143	128	137	133	16	130	7	20	13	3	139	870
		144	2	17	8	12	129	15	138	125	132	6	142	870
©IJT		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

13x13	mgc														1105
		82	87	86	91	79	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105
		89	85	81	92	78	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105
		84	83	88	74	96	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105
		80	76	77	95	97	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105
		90	94	93	73	75	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105
		100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105
		70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105
		122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105
		48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105
		136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105
		34	142	40	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105
		14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105
		156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105
©IJT		1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

14x14	mgc														1379	
		97	102	91	104	83	114	77	120	132	65	169	28	192	5	1379
		92	103	98	101	111	86	117	80	66	131	149	48	183	14	1379
		106	93	100	95	115	82	130	67	60	137	159	38	13	184	1379
		99	96	105	94	88	109	123	74	134	63	45	152	171	26	1379
		113	81	112	108	87	90	72	125	51	146	158	39	178	19	1379
		84	116	85	89	107	110	69	128	139	58	150	47	11	186	1379
		79	70	68	126	122	78	124	121	61	136	164	33	7	190	1379
		118	127	129	71	75	119	76	73	144	53	40	157	23	174	1379
		49	64	50	62	145	54	140	138	142	141	42	155	25	172	1379
		148	133	147	135	52	143	57	59	56	55	31	166	17	180	1379
		46	27	35	168	167	153	163	41	160	36	32	154	189	8	1379
		151	170	162	29	30	44	34	156	37	161	43	165	182	15	1379
		194	187	16	1	177	195	6	21	24	12	4	175	179	188	1379
		3	10	181	196	20	2	191	176	173	185	193	22	9	18	1379
©IJT		1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

15x15	mgc															1695	
		110	117	112	125	101	127	99	144	82	67	159	52	174	9	217	1695
		115	113	111	124	102	133	93	142	84	64	162	41	185	3	223	1695
		114	109	116	104	122	94	132	79	147	167	59	40	186	8	218	1695
		108	106	123	107	121	89	137	78	148	168	58	184	42	205	21	1695
		118	120	103	105	119	92	134	140	86	63	163	50	176	7	219	1695
		90	91	131	128	129	126	96	138	88	62	164	191	35	201	25	1695
		136	135	95	98	97	130	100	146	80	171	55	195	31	213	13	1695
		149	153	87	83	81	151	85	76	152	172	54	190	36	206	20	1695
		77	73	139	143	145	75	141	74	150	71	155	45	181	1	225	1695
		70	60	69	170	165	72	169	66	68	173	161	51	175	203	23	1695
		156	166	157	56	61	154	57	160	158	65	53	196	30	6	220	1695
		180	34	182	183	179	32	187	33	177	38	178	37	29	215	11	1695
		46	192	44	43	47	194	39	193	49	188	48	197	189	10	216	1695
		224	221	211	26	17	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	27	210	28	1695
		2	5	15	200	209	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	199	198	16	1695
©IJT		1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

16x16	mgc															2056		
		127	132	121	134	115	142	147	110	162	95	77	180	212	45	240	17	2056
		122	133	128	131	141	116	108	149	85	172	190	67	55	202	10	247	2056
		136	123	130	125	113	144	158	99	94	163	64	193	40	217	230	27	2056
		129	126	135	124	119	138	155	102	167	90	60	197	38	219	236	21	2056
		145	118	143	117	137	111	152	105	168	89	182	75	224	33	233	24	2056
		112	139	114	140	146	120	107	150	84	173	184	73	41	216	241	16	2056
		101	160	157	148	106	104	98	154	176	81	78	179	51	206	13	244	2056
		156	97	100	109	151	153	103	159	174	83	63	194	221	36	7	250	2056
		80	169	178	171	96	166	92	87	82	164	183	74	205	52	14	243	2056
		177	88	79	86	161	91	165	170	93	175	199	58	207	50	256	1	2056
		189	57	188	195	71	76	59	65	70	185	196	191	32	225	248	9	2056
		68	200	69	62	186	181	198	192	187	72	66	61	209	48	29	228	2056
		47	215	53	35	226	211	43	34	54	201	208	39	220	213	8	249	2056
		210	42	204	222	31	46	214	223	203	56	49	218	44	37	23	234	2056
		4	254	232	15	239	22	2	246	20	26	245	252	6	28	238	227	2056
		253	3	25	242	18	235	255	11	237	231	12	5	251	229	30	19	2056
©IJT		2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

17x17	mgc																2465		
		146	147	142	157	133	132	158	119	171	203	87	62	228	50	240	271	19	2465
		141	145	149	156	134	125	165	181	109	198	92	216	74	53	237	258	32	2465
		148	143	144	136	154	128	162	114	176	99	191	210	80	254	36	4	286	2465
		150	152	135	137	151	169	121	118	172	205	85	212	78	54	236	2	288	2465
		140	138	155	139	153	167	123	117	173	201	89	69	221	255	35	270	20	2465
		126	122	161	124	160	163	159	182	108	202	88	63	227	57	233	267	23	2465
		164	168	129	166	130	131	127	180	110	93	197	211	79	41	249	5	285	2465
		179	105	177	107	175	112	106	174	170	101	189	214	76	251	39	261	29	2465
		111	185	113	183	115	178	184	120	116	95	195	68	222	253	37	263	27	2465
		103	193	204	100	98	102	200	96	199	104	196	207	83	55	235	8	282	2465
		187	97	86	190	192	188	90	194	91	94	186	215	75	60	230	10	280	2465
		206	66	64	218	61	209	67	213	208	220	71	65	217	47	243	14	276	2465
		84	224	226	72	229	81	223	77	82	70	219	73	225	245	45	265	25	2465
		239	42	40	241	232	44	234	231	43	242	238	38	33	244	34	15	275	2465
		51	248	250	49	58	246	56	59	247	48	52	252	257	256	46	264	26	2465
		289	284	24	17	18	277	281	283	31	278	16	21	22	287	279	28	30	2465
		1	6	266	273	272	13	9	7	259	12	274	269	268	3	11	260	262	2465
©IJT		2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

18x18	mgc																	2925		
		161	166	155	168	178	147	181	144	204	121	226	99	85	240	61	264	28	297	2925
		156	167	162	165	177	148	142	183	207	118	221	104	66	259	281	44	312	13	2925
		170	157	164	159	146	179	140	185	126	199	219	106	71	254	270	55	34	291	2925
		163	160	169	158	150	175	135	190	115	210	105	220	255	70	46	279	11	314	2925
		153	145	176	154	173	174	137	188	125	200	213	112	83	242	262	63	3	322	2925
		172	180	149	171	151	152	186	139	212	113	108	217	74	251	64	261	33	292	2925
		132	189	131	143	191	184	192	138	114	211	223	102	252	73	282	43	296	29	2925
		193	136	194	182	134	141	187	133	202	123	109	216	81	244	273	52	18	307	2925
		127	117	203	197	195	209	205	129	119	124	233	92	247	78	286	39	308	17	2925
		198	208	122	128	130	116	120	196	201	206	98	227	245	80	35	290	305	20	2925
		111	91	224	107	215	94	96	228	232	222	100	230	237	88	38	287	302	23	2925
		214	234	101	218	110	231	229	97	93	103	95	225	82	243	263	62	318	7	2925
		90	239	248	67	68	246	250	249	89	260	72	87	241	69	40	285	19	306	2925
		235	86	77	258	257	79	75	76	236	65	253	238	256	84	59	266	304	21	2925
		45	36	288	47	41	54	267	276	53	274	60	275	277	56	283	268	311	14	2925
		280	289	37	278	284	271	58	49	272	51	265	50	48	269	57	42	1	324	2925
		22	16	319	5	24	9	323	300	8	32	321	294	313	310	26	10	295	298	2925
		303	309	6	320	301	316	2	25	317	293	4	31	12	15	299	315	27	30	2925
©IJT		2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

19x19	mgc																		3439		
		184	177	182	192	170	204	158	220	142	132	230	100	262	83	279	308	54	360	2	3439
		179	181	183	193	169	167	195	216	146	138	224	248	114	266	96	299	63	355	7	3439
		180	185	178	172	190	165	197	214	148	234	128	103	259	269	93	300	62	353	9	3439
		174	176	191	175	189	202	160	150	212	134	228	98	264	271	91	302	60	354	8	3439
		188	186	171	173	187	163	199	218	144	137	225	246	116	74	288	37	325	359	3	3439
		157	201	196	159	162	198	194	149	213	139	223	253	109	280	82	53	309	347	15	3439
		205	161	166	203	200	168	164	154	208	237	125	99	263	272	90	47	315	351	11	3439
		143	141	209	207	211	215	145	152	206	235	127	243	119	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439
		219	221	153	155	151	147	217	156	210	241	121	257	105	270	92	39	323	348	14	3439
		123	129	232	126	226	229	231	222	227	124	122	244	118	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439
		239	233	130	236	136	133	131	140	135	240	238	108	254	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439
		107	247	106	102	104	101	249	252	97	251	245	242	250	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439
		255	115	256	260	258	261	113	110	265	111	117	112	120	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439
		293	80	94	85	291	89	284	95	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	294	68	34	328	3439
		69	282	268	277	71	273	78	267	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439
		307	301	40	50	51	298	44	49	306	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439
		55	61	322	312	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439
		356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439
		6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439
©IJT		3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

20x20	mgc																				4010
	199	204	193	206	214	187	180	221	157	244	254	147	124	277	311	90	45	356	384	17	4010
	194	205	200	203	215	186	170	231	158	243	258	143	106	295	97	304	337	64	373	28	4010
	208	195	202	197	192	209	229	172	239	162	137	264	296	105	93	308	338	63	26	375	4010
	201	198	207	196	184	217	228	173	235	166	257	144	287	114	326	75	66	335	13	388	4010
	212	218	210	190	185	188	177	224	249	152	130	271	126	275	319	82	70	331	399	2	4010
	189	183	191	211	213	216	171	230	160	241	270	131	104	297	306	95	39	362	381	20	4010
	182	220	175	176	223	232	222	174	163	238	261	140	276	125	300	101	341	60	5	396	4010
	219	181	226	225	178	169	227	179	248	153	150	251	120	281	320	81	59	342	14	387	4010
	155	154	167	156	250	240	236	168	237	242	136	265	280	121	89	312	360	41	15	386	4010
	246	247	234	245	151	161	165	233	159	164	272	129	112	289	94	307	49	352	365	36	4010
	255	263	142	135	260	148	256	134	262	133	149	269	278	123	77	324	346	55	397	4	4010
	146	138	259	266	141	253	145	267	139	268	132	252	109	292	88	313	336	65	9	392	4010
	282	286	108	279	111	118	288	127	116	294	273	117	298	110	328	73	68	333	37	364	4010
	119	115	293	122	290	283	113	274	285	107	128	284	291	103	76	325	51	350	8	393	4010
	314	321	85	96	323	315	98	79	92	310	84	299	74	99	301	318	343	58	400	1	4010
	87	80	316	305	78	86	303	322	309	91	317	102	327	302	83	100	355	46	6	395	4010
	357	69	72	349	56	43	359	48	47	334	351	348	40	340	330	347	62	57	367	34	4010
	44	332	329	52	345	358	42	353	354	67	50	53	361	61	71	54	344	339	379	22	4010
	33	370	29	16	27	391	18	366	377	21	12	11	371	376	32	23	382	398	394	363	4010
	368	31	372	385	374	10	383	35	24	380	389	390	30	25	369	378	19	3	38	7	4010
©IJT	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

21x21	mgc																					4641	
		222	217	224	233	209	242	200	182	260	180	262	158	284	329	113	102	340	61	381	24	418	4641
		223	221	219	232	210	206	236	183	259	271	171	305	137	133	309	98	344	368	74	441	1	4641
		218	225	220	212	230	243	199	249	193	277	165	157	285	129	313	359	83	367	75	34	408	4641
		214	216	231	215	229	244	198	247	195	174	268	153	289	325	117	107	335	375	67	433	9	4641
		228	226	211	213	227	204	238	253	189	170	272	299	143	134	308	97	345	376	66	32	410	4641
		197	240	235	234	201	203	237	185	257	175	267	149	293	323	119	352	90	44	398	31	411	4641
		245	202	207	208	241	205	239	252	190	178	264	298	144	318	124	108	334	379	63	434	8	4641
		255	248	184	188	181	186	251	246	250	176	266	151	291	324	118	96	346	369	73	432	10	4641
		187	194	258	254	261	256	191	192	196	276	166	302	140	125	317	364	78	372	70	436	6	4641
		274	162	269	265	167	270	163	263	164	273	161	301	141	132	310	356	86	41	401	431	11	4641
		168	280	173	177	275	172	279	179	278	281	169	150	292	333	109	105	337	388	54	435	7	4641
		155	160	159	294	145	295	156	154	303	152	300	304	296	127	315	104	338	53	389	29	413	4641
		287	282	283	148	297	147	286	288	139	290	142	146	138	331	111	91	351	57	385	35	407	4641
		130	123	328	322	327	128	330	135	332	121	320	126	131	136	326	349	93	373	69	430	12	4641
		312	319	114	120	115	314	112	307	110	321	122	316	311	116	306	357	85	48	394	27	415	4641
		339	80	348	79	336	353	341	81	88	82	84	342	350	87	343	347	77	46	396	429	13	4641
		103	362	94	363	106	89	101	361	354	360	358	100	92	355	99	365	95	56	386	30	412	4641
		52	371	383	55	380	42	49	45	384	51	370	377	50	47	378	43	374	366	382	19	423	4641
		390	71	59	387	62	400	393	397	58	391	72	65	392	395	64	399	68	60	76	421	21	4641
		402	426	17	409	22	14	18	5	15	417	405	419	3	406	414	403	4	2	416	20	404	4641
		40	16	425	33	420	428	424	437	427	25	37	23	439	36	28	39	438	440	26	38	422	4641
©IJT		4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641

23x23	mgc																					6095			
		262	267	266	260	270	278	252	296	234	313	217	193	337	372	158	150	380	436	94	63	467	24	506	6095
		269	265	261	258	272	244	286	290	240	312	218	204	326	370	160	395	135	119	411	484	46	527	3	6095
		264	263	268	275	255	241	289	227	303	309	221	199	331	377	153	405	125	114	416	471	59	44	486	6095
		277	276	256	259	257	284	246	232	298	308	222	196	334	170	360	139	391	105	425	71	459	521	9	6095
		253	254	274	273	271	280	250	228	302	314	216	340	190	167	363	400	130	432	98	472	58	518	12	6095
		242	283	282	245	243	279	281	229	301	207	323	203	327	373	157	143	387	102	428	84	446	525	5	6095
		288	247	248	285	287	249	251	295	235	212	318	343	187	376	154	409	121	118	412	468	62	32	498	6095
		305	299	237	304	238	230	236	297	239	206	324	339	191	169	361	149	381	429	101	481	49	26	504	6095
		225	231	293	226	292	300	294	291	233	210	320	342	188	162	368	403	127	431	99	78	452	513	17	6095
		307	215	208	209	317	211	306	205	311	310	316	341	189	374	156	146	384	120	410	82	448	23	507	6095
		223	315	322	321	213	319	224	325	219	214	220	201	329	174	356	398	132	104	426	64	466	524	6	6095
		338	348	346	345	197	195	194	202	347	198	349	200	186	171	359	147	383	430	100	465	65	43	487	6095
		192	182	184	185	333	335	336	328	183	332	181	344	330	176	354	399	131	117	413	60	470	27	503	6095
		163	351	159	161	164	155	358	352	165	355	357	168	353	364	350	397	133	435	95	67	463	508	22	6095
		367	179	371	369	366	375	172	178	365	175	173	362	177	180	166	137	393	112	418	75	455	514	16	6095
		151	389	408	407	142	404	402	401	138	140	148	145	144	134	406	152	394	442	88	480	50	516	14	6095
		379	141	122	123	388	126	128	129	392	390	382	385	386	396	124	136	378	437	93	81	449	41	489	6095
		111	440	110	103	444	108	439	443	115	109	441	116	434	113	106	97	438	445	423	483	47	512	18	6095
		419	90	420	427	86	422	91	87	415	421	89	414	96	417	424	433	92	107	85	482	48	25	505	6095
		453	451	447	454	57	53	457	54	460	55	458	450	61	462	456	52	56	51	464	69	45	28	502	6095
		77	79	83	76	473	477	73	476	70	475	72	80	469	68	74	478	474	479	66	485	461	42	488	6095
		1	501	10	13	490	499	491	7	11	493	509	497	510	495	492	15	8	19	500	4	494	34	2	6095
		529	29	520	517	40	31	39	523	519	37	21	33	20	35	38	515	522	511	30	526	36	528	496	6095
©IJT		6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095	6095

24x24	mgc																							6924		
		287	292	281	294	299	278	318	259	323	254	340	237	363	214	162	415	417	160	126	451	492	85	569	8	6924
		282	293	288	291	279	298	310	267	335	242	359	218	386	191	413	164	450	127	90	487	75	502	4	573	6924
		296	283	290	285	306	271	260	317	247	330	354	223	210	367	175	402	143	434	472	105	497	80	30	547	6924
		289	286	295	284	273	304	262	315	244	333	339	238	205	372	390	187	149	428	454	123	519	58	535	42	6924
		280	301	300	303	272	275	266	311	256	321	220	357	382	195	408	169	142	435	116	461	65	512	25	552	6924
		297	276	277	274	302	305	314	263	322	255	222	355	193	384	190	387	427	150	109	468	499	78	20	557	6924
		270	308	257	319	309	316	265	264	243	334	236	341	209	368	165	412	446	131	120	457	526	51	17	560	6924
		307	269	320	258	268	261	313	312	327	250	230	347	362	215	403	174	440	137	112	465	67	510	565	12	6924
		329	253	328	240	338	246	332	326	252	241	232	345	374	203	184	393	431	146	91	486	521	56	28	549	6924
		248	324	249	337	239	331	245	251	336	325	235	342	380	197	398	179	136	441	102	475	516	61	21	556	6924
		217	234	350	344	351	229	221	353	358	225	349	231	204	373	406	171	135	442	453	124	489	88	15	562	6924
		360	343	227	233	226	348	356	224	219	352	346	228	199	378	409	168	157	420	483	94	507	70	32	545	6924
		361	385	206	212	370	202	369	211	379	364	200	383	196	201	172	405	155	422	474	103	47	530	576	1	6924
		216	192	371	365	207	375	208	366	198	213	377	194	376	381	181	396	140	437	101	476	491	86	39	538	6924
		395	185	189	163	407	161	397	399	188	401	186	173	167	400	394	411	424	153	469	108	77	500	574	3	6924
		182	392	388	414	170	416	180	178	389	176	391	404	410	177	166	183	421	156	488	89	69	508	554	23	6924
		429	438	151	439	432	425	419	449	436	129	154	159	144	445	147	134	133	130	473	104	64	513	546	31	6924
		148	139	426	138	145	152	158	128	141	448	423	418	433	132	430	443	447	444	471	106	83	494	536	41	6924
		111	452	115	479	458	464	100	459	107	96	97	122	95	463	485	117	484	121	467	478	498	79	553	24	6924
		466	125	462	98	119	113	477	118	470	481	480	455	482	114	92	460	93	456	99	110	84	493	18	559	6924
		514	76	49	517	520	506	73	515	509	82	55	527	59	496	72	48	52	523	511	53	87	503	570	7	6924
		63	501	528	60	57	71	504	62	68	495	522	50	518	81	505	529	525	54	66	524	74	490	537	40	6924
		567	14	532	19	575	550	548	561	534	566	571	13	33	541	46	9	35	34	539	44	540	26	5	22	6924
		10	563	45	558	2	27	29	16	43	11	6	564	544	36	531	568	542	543	38	533	37	551	555	572	6924
©IJT		6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924

25x25	mgc																								7825	
	310	315	314	308	318	326	300	344	282	361	265	241	385	420	206	198	428	484	142	111	515	72	554	47	579	7825
	317	313	309	306	320	292	334	338	288	360	266	252	374	418	208	443	183	167	459	532	94	575	51	43	583	7825
	312	311	316	323	303	289	337	275	351	357	269	247	379	425	201	453	173	162	464	520	106	92	534	45	581	7825
	325	324	304	307	305	332	294	280	346	356	270	244	382	218	408	187	439	153	473	119	507	569	57	41	585	7825
	301	302	322	321	319	328	298	276	350	362	264	388	238	215	411	448	178	480	146	519	107	566	60	39	587	7825
	290	331	330	293	291	327	329	277	349	255	371	251	375	421	205	191	435	150	476	132	494	573	53	37	589	7825
	336	295	296	333	335	297	299	343	283	260	366	391	235	424	202	457	169	166	460	516	110	80	546	35	591	7825
	353	347	285	352	286	278	284	345	287	254	372	387	239	217	409	197	429	477	149	529	97	74	552	33	593	7825
	273	279	341	274	340	348	342	339	281	258	368	390	236	210	416	451	175	479	147	126	500	561	65	31	595	7825
	355	263	256	257	365	259	354	253	359	358	364	389	237	422	204	194	432	168	458	130	496	71	555	29	597	7825
	271	363	370	369	261	367	272	373	267	262	268	249	377	222	404	446	180	152	474	112	514	572	54	27	599	7825
	386	396	394	393	245	243	242	250	395	246	397	248	234	219	407	195	431	478	148	513	113	91	535	25	601	7825
	240	230	232	233	381	383	384	376	231	380	229	392	378	224	402	447	179	165	461	108	518	75	551	605	21	7825
	211	399	207	209	212	203	406	400	213	403	405	216	401	412	398	445	181	483	143	115	511	556	70	607	19	7825
	415	227	419	417	414	423	220	226	413	223	221	410	225	228	214	185	441	160	466	123	503	562	64	609	17	7825
	199	437	456	455	190	452	450	449	186	188	196	193	192	182	454	200	442	490	136	528	98	564	62	611	15	7825
	427	189	170	171	436	174	176	177	440	438	430	433	434	444	172	184	426	485	141	129	497	89	537	613	13	7825
	159	488	158	151	492	156	487	491	163	157	489	164	482	161	154	145	486	493	471	531	95	560	66	615	11	7825
	467	138	468	475	134	470	139	135	463	469	137	462	144	465	472	481	140	155	133	530	96	73	553	617	9	7825
	501	499	495	502	105	101	505	102	508	103	506	498	109	510	504	100	104	99	512	117	93	76	550	619	7	7825
	125	127	131	124	521	525	121	524	118	523	120	128	517	116	122	526	522	527	114	533	509	90	536	621	5	7825
	49	549	58	61	538	547	539	55	59	541	557	545	558	543	540	63	56	67	548	52	542	82	50	623	3	7825
	577	77	568	565	88	79	87	571	567	85	69	81	68	83	86	563	570	559	78	574	84	576	544	625	1	7825
	598	580	582	584	586	588	590	592	594	596	578	23	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	602	600	7825
	28	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	30	48	603	604	606	608	610	612	614	616	618	620	622	624	26	24	7825
©IJT	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

26x26	mgc																									8801			
		337	342	331	344	349	328	307	370	293	384	273	404	251	426	448	229	181	496	152	525	559	118	609	68	3	674	8801	
		332	343	338	341	354	323	368	309	292	385	271	406	266	411	212	465	201	476	164	513	539	138	77	600	1	676	8801	
		346	333	340	335	326	351	320	357	302	375	286	391	257	420	232	445	199	478	511	166	553	124	626	51	46	631	8801	
		339	336	345	334	330	347	359	318	379	298	397	280	417	260	457	220	494	183	504	173	555	122	78	599	4	673	8801	
		324	321	352	329	350	355	310	367	376	301	393	284	427	250	438	239	479	198	172	505	133	544	79	598	650	27	8801	
		353	356	325	348	322	327	313	364	296	381	268	409	258	419	240	437	184	493	528	149	109	568	93	584	652	25	8801	
		358	316	360	314	315	369	365	311	377	300	408	269	421	256	215	462	482	195	144	533	577	100	63	614	12	665	8801	
		319	361	317	363	362	308	366	312	378	299	395	282	247	430	459	218	495	182	536	141	570	107	65	612	15	662	8801	
		374	382	383	373	289	386	306	297	305	290	400	277	413	264	223	454	473	204	502	175	119	558	71	606	38	639	8801	
		303	295	294	304	388	291	371	380	387	372	281	396	248	429	439	238	475	202	139	538	130	547	58	619	42	635	8801	
		394	272	392	410	402	399	288	270	276	398	287	274	242	435	217	460	207	470	517	160	548	129	592	85	45	632	8801	
		283	405	285	267	275	278	389	407	401	279	403	390	433	244	234	443	491	186	531	146	112	565	70	607	646	31	8801	
		415	254	245	253	255	431	412	418	263	428	261	436	425	243	461	216	178	499	519	158	113	564	625	52	642	35	8801	
		262	423	432	424	422	246	265	259	414	249	416	241	434	252	228	449	187	490	169	508	551	126	582	95	675	2	8801	
		236	440	456	226	222	213	466	219	446	444	235	224	452	447	463	227	480	197	145	532	128	549	64	613	26	651	8801	
		441	237	221	451	455	464	211	458	231	233	442	453	225	230	450	214	209	468	148	529	550	127	585	92	667	10	8801	
		472	481	484	194	488	489	467	191	477	500	492	203	208	192	206	190	180	179	176	501	572	105	622	55	11	666	8801	
		205	196	193	483	189	188	210	486	200	177	185	474	469	485	471	487	498	497	156	521	98	579	593	84	17	660	8801	
		163	518	153	506	140	526	150	161	157	510	503	509	530	162	534	523	170	165	535	155	563	114	611	66	672	5	8801	
		514	159	524	171	537	151	527	516	520	167	174	168	147	515	143	154	507	512	522	142	97	580	88	589	649	28	8801	
		135	106	103	111	561	131	569	102	560	573	557	132	125	115	556	576	541	554	99	567	134	540	597	80	664	13	8801	
		542	571	574	566	116	546	108	575	117	104	120	545	552	562	121	101	136	123	578	110	137	543	624	53	645	32	8801	
		623	86	608	595	601	59	91	604	605	74	615	87	57	583	594	61	610	587	602	96	60	89	56	81	23	654	8801	
		54	591	69	82	76	618	586	73	72	603	62	590	620	94	83	616	67	90	75	581	617	588	596	621	643	34	8801	
		50	633	37	47	40	658	641	14	636	644	670	6	634	30	8	16	655	638	653	648	659	49	48	9	657	21	8801	
		627	44	640	630	637	19	36	663	41	33	7	671	43	647	669	661	22	39	24	29	18	628	629	668	656	20	8801	
©IJT		8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801

27x27	mgc																										9855		
	362	367	366	360	370	378	352	396	334	413	317	293	437	472	258	250	480	536	194	163	567	124	606	99	631	51	679	9855	
	369	365	361	358	372	344	386	390	340	412	318	304	426	470	260	495	235	219	511	584	146	627	103	95	635	45	685	9855	
	364	363	368	375	355	341	389	327	403	409	321	299	431	477	253	505	225	214	516	572	158	144	586	97	633	47	683	9855	
	377	376	356	359	357	384	346	332	398	408	322	296	434	270	460	239	491	205	525	171	559	621	109	93	637	49	681	9855	
	353	354	374	373	371	380	350	328	402	414	316	440	290	267	463	500	230	532	198	571	159	618	112	91	639	43	687	9855	
	342	383	382	345	343	379	381	329	401	307	423	303	427	473	257	243	487	202	528	184	546	624	106	89	641	41	689	9855	
	388	347	348	385	387	349	351	395	335	312	418	443	287	476	254	509	221	218	512	568	162	132	598	87	643	39	691	9855	
	405	399	337	404	338	330	336	397	339	306	424	439	291	269	461	249	481	529	201	581	149	126	604	85	645	37	693	9855	
	325	331	393	326	392	400	394	391	333	310	420	442	288	262	468	503	227	220	510	178	552	613	117	83	647	35	695	9855	
	407	315	308	309	417	311	406	305	411	410	416	441	289	474	256	498	232	531	199	182	548	123	607	81	649	33	697	9855	
	323	415	422	421	313	419	324	425	319	314	320	301	429	274	456	246	484	204	526	164	566	625	105	79	651	31	699	9855	
	438	448	446	445	297	295	294	302	447	298	449	300	286	271	459	247	483	530	200	565	165	143	587	77	653	29	701	9855	
	292	282	284	285	433	435	436	428	283	432	281	444	430	276	454	499	231	217	513	160	570	127	603	657	73	27	703	9855	
	263	451	259	261	264	255	458	452	265	455	457	268	453	464	450	497	233	535	195	167	563	608	122	659	71	707	23	9855	
	467	279	471	469	466	475	272	278	465	275	273	462	277	280	266	237	493	212	518	175	555	614	116	661	69	709	21	9855	
	251	489	508	507	242	504	502	501	238	240	248	245	244	234	506	252	494	542	188	580	150	616	114	663	67	711	19	9855	
	479	241	222	223	488	226	228	229	492	490	482	485	486	496	224	236	478	537	193	181	549	141	589	665	65	713	17	9855	
	211	540	210	203	544	208	539	543	215	209	541	216	534	213	206	197	538	545	523	583	147	612	118	667	63	715	15	9855	
	519	190	520	527	186	522	191	187	515	521	189	514	196	517	524	533	192	207	185	582	148	125	605	669	61	717	13	9855	
	553	551	547	554	157	153	557	154	560	155	558	550	161	562	556	152	156	151	564	169	145	128	602	671	59	719	11	9855	
	177	179	183	176	573	577	173	576	170	575	172	180	569	168	174	578	574	579	166	585	561	142	588	673	57	721	9	9855	
	101	601	110	113	590	599	591	107	111	593	609	597	610	595	592	115	108	119	600	104	594	134	102	675	55	723	7	9855	
	629	129	620	617	140	131	139	623	619	137	121	133	120	135	138	615	622	611	130	626	136	628	596	677	53	725	5	9855	
	650	632	634	636	638	640	642	644	646	648	630	75	74	72	70	68	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	654	652	727	3	9855	
	80	98	96	94	92	90	88	86	84	82	100	655	656	658	660	662	664	666	668	670	672	674	676	78	76	729	1	9855	
	700	680	682	684	686	688	690	692	694	696	698	678	25	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	704	702	9855	
	30	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	52	705	706	708	710	712	714	716	718	720	722	724	726	728	28	26	9855	
©IJT	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855

28x28	mgc																											10990		
		391	396	385	398	403	382	361	424	347	438	327	458	305	480	502	283	235	550	206	579	613	172	663	122	57	728	39	746	10990
		386	397	392	395	408	377	422	363	346	439	325	460	320	465	266	519	255	530	218	567	593	192	131	654	55	730	37	748	10990
		400	387	394	389	380	405	374	411	356	429	340	445	311	474	286	499	253	532	565	220	607	178	680	105	100	685	747	38	10990
		393	390	399	388	384	401	413	372	433	352	451	334	471	314	511	274	548	237	558	227	609	176	132	653	704	81	745	40	10990
		378	375	406	383	404	409	364	421	430	355	447	338	481	304	492	293	533	252	226	559	187	598	147	638	58	727	749	36	10990
		407	410	379	402	376	381	367	418	350	435	322	463	312	473	294	491	238	547	582	203	163	622	124	661	706	79	35	750	10990
		412	370	414	368	369	423	419	365	431	354	462	323	475	310	269	516	536	249	198	587	631	154	117	668	66	719	751	34	10990
		373	415	371	417	416	362	420	366	432	353	449	336	301	484	513	272	549	236	590	195	624	161	119	666	69	716	33	752	10990
		428	436	437	427	343	440	360	351	359	344	454	331	467	318	277	508	527	258	556	229	173	612	125	660	92	693	753	32	10990
		357	349	348	358	442	345	425	434	441	426	335	450	302	483	493	292	529	256	193	592	184	601	112	673	96	689	754	31	10990
		448	326	446	464	456	453	342	324	330	452	341	328	296	489	271	514	261	524	571	214	602	183	646	139	99	686	30	755	10990
		337	459	339	321	329	332	443	461	455	333	457	444	487	298	288	497	545	240	585	200	166	619	133	652	700	85	29	756	10990
		469	308	299	307	309	485	466	472	317	482	315	490	479	297	515	270	232	553	573	212	167	618	679	106	696	89	14	771	10990
		316	477	486	478	476	300	319	313	468	303	470	295	488	306	282	503	241	544	223	562	605	180	636	149	729	56	41	744	10990
		290	494	510	280	276	267	520	273	500	498	289	278	506	501	517	281	534	251	199	586	182	603	118	667	80	705	759	26	10990
		495	291	275	505	509	518	265	512	285	287	496	507	279	284	504	268	263	522	202	583	604	181	639	146	721	64	760	25	10990
		526	535	538	248	542	543	521	245	531	554	546	257	262	246	260	244	234	233	230	555	626	159	676	109	65	720	24	761	10990
		259	250	247	537	243	242	264	540	254	231	239	528	523	539	525	541	552	551	210	575	152	633	647	138	71	714	762	23	10990
		217	572	207	560	194	580	204	215	211	564	557	563	584	216	588	577	224	219	589	209	617	168	665	120	726	59	22	763	10990
		568	213	578	225	591	205	581	570	574	221	228	222	201	569	197	208	561	566	576	196	151	634	142	643	703	82	764	21	10990
		189	160	157	165	615	185	623	156	614	627	611	186	179	169	610	630	595	608	153	621	188	594	651	134	718	67	20	765	10990
		596	625	628	620	170	600	162	629	171	158	174	599	606	616	175	155	190	177	632	164	191	597	678	107	699	86	766	19	10990
		677	140	662	649	655	113	145	658	659	128	669	141	111	637	648	115	664	641	656	150	114	143	110	135	77	708	18	767	10990
		108	645	123	136	130	672	640	127	126	657	116	644	674	148	137	670	121	144	129	635	671	642	650	675	697	88	768	17	10990
		104	687	101	91	94	712	695	68	690	698	724	60	688	84	62	70	709	692	707	702	713	103	102	63	711	75	16	769	10990
		681	98	684	694	691	73	90	717	95	87	61	725	97	701	723	715	76	93	78	83	72	682	683	722	710	74	770	15	10990
		42	742	44	740	46	738	48	736	50	734	52	732	54	1	13	773	11	775	9	777	7	779	5	781	3	783	757	758	10990
		743	43	741	45	739	47	737	49	735	51	733	53	731	784	772	12	774	10	776	8	778	6	780	4	782	2	27	28	10990
©IJT		10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990

29x29	mgc																												12209	
	418	423	422	416	426	434	408	452	390	469	373	349	493	528	314	306	536	592	250	219	623	180	662	155	687	107	735	815	27	12209
	425	421	417	414	428	400	442	446	396	468	374	360	482	526	316	551	291	275	567	640	202	683	159	151	691	101	741	824	18	12209
	420	419	424	431	411	397	445	383	459	465	377	355	487	533	309	561	281	270	572	628	214	200	642	153	689	103	739	28	814	12209
	433	432	412	415	413	440	402	388	454	464	378	352	490	326	516	295	547	261	581	227	615	677	165	149	693	105	737	32	810	12209
	409	410	430	429	427	436	406	384	458	470	372	496	346	323	519	556	286	588	254	627	215	674	168	147	695	99	743	46	796	12209
	398	439	438	401	399	435	437	385	457	363	479	359	483	529	313	299	543	258	584	240	602	680	162	145	697	97	745	820	22	12209
	444	403	404	441	443	405	407	451	391	368	474	499	343	532	310	565	277	274	568	624	218	188	654	143	699	95	747	36	806	12209
	461	455	393	460	394	386	392	453	395	362	480	495	347	325	517	305	537	585	257	637	205	182	660	141	701	93	749	818	24	12209
	381	387	449	382	448	456	450	447	389	366	476	498	344	318	524	559	283	276	566	231	611	669	173	139	703	91	751	42	800	12209
	463	371	364	365	473	367	462	361	467	466	472	497	345	530	312	554	288	587	255	238	604	179	663	137	705	89	753	52	790	12209
	379	471	478	477	369	475	380	481	375	370	376	357	485	330	512	302	540	260	582	220	622	681	161	135	707	87	755	834	8	12209
	494	504	502	501	353	351	350	358	503	354	505	356	342	327	515	303	539	586	256	621	221	199	643	133	709	85	757	38	804	12209
	348	338	340	341	489	491	492	484	339	488	337	500	486	332	510	555	287	273	569	216	626	183	659	713	129	83	759	40	802	12209
	319	507	315	317	320	311	514	508	321	511	513	324	509	520	506	553	289	591	251	223	619	664	178	715	127	763	79	50	792	12209
	523	335	527	525	522	531	328	334	521	331	329	518	333	336	322	293	549	268	574	234	608	670	172	717	125	765	77	48	794	12209
	307	545	564	563	298	560	558	557	294	296	304	301	300	290	562	308	550	598	244	636	206	672	170	719	123	767	75	816	26	12209
	535	297	278	279	544	282	284	285	548	546	538	541	542	552	280	292	534	593	249	237	605	197	645	721	121	769	73	822	20	12209
	267	596	266	259	600	264	595	599	271	265	597	272	590	269	262	253	594	601	579	639	203	668	174	723	119	771	71	832	10	12209
	575	246	576	583	242	578	247	243	571	577	245	570	252	573	580	589	248	263	241	638	204	181	661	725	117	773	69	830	12	12209
	609	607	616	610	213	209	613	210	603	211	614	606	217	618	612	208	212	207	620	225	201	184	658	727	115	775	67	828	14	12209
	233	235	226	232	629	633	229	632	239	631	228	236	625	224	230	634	630	635	222	641	617	198	644	729	113	777	65	34	808	12209
	157	657	166	169	646	655	163	647	167	649	665	653	666	651	648	171	164	175	656	160	650	190	158	731	111	779	63	826	16	12209
	685	185	676	673	196	187	679	195	675	193	177	189	176	191	194	671	678	667	186	682	192	684	652	733	109	781	61	30	812	12209
	706	688	690	694	692	696	698	700	702	704	686	131	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	112	110	710	708	783	59	836	6	12209
	136	154	152	148	150	146	144	142	140	138	156	711	712	714	716	718	720	722	724	726	728	730	732	134	132	785	57	840	2	12209
	756	736	738	740	742	744	746	748	750	752	754	734	81	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	66	64	62	60	58	760	758	838	4	12209
	86	106	104	102	100	98	96	94	92	90	88	108	761	762	764	766	768	770	772	774	776	778	780	782	784	84	82	44	798	12209
	811	813	807	19	789	13	9	3	793	803	11	795	801	25	809	805	5	1	17	23	21	797	791	799	787	7	15	54	786	12209
	31	29	35	823	53	829	833	839	49	39	831	47	41	817	33	37	837	841	825	819	821	45	51	43	55	835	827	56	788	12209
©IJT	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209

Acknowledgement

Most of the results are done manually. Few case of lower orders are done by a software by H. White [1]. The author is thankful to H. White for providing the script.

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- **Block-Wise Magic Squares**
- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
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